

A Robust CWM–PCA for Chemospace: Horn-based Dimensioning, Principal-angle Stability, and Dirichlet Pooling of Isomers

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Abstract

We present a community-weighted PCA for species chemospace. Compounds are aggregated to species with two weightings: presence (detection proportion) and relative (softmax of log-abundance). Isomer candidates are pooled using Dirichlet priors (A1 symmetric; A2 similarity-weighted). Dimensions are selected by Horn's parallel analysis, and robustness is assessed with leave-one-out principal angles. Of 22 descriptors, nine were near-constant or missing and were excluded. Variance concentrated in two components: presence 55.7% and 28.4%; relative 75.8% and 15.5%; both PCs exceeded the 95th percentile noise envelope. The PC1 and PC2 subspace was stable (mean cosine 0.993 to 0.994; largest deletion about 22 degrees), and A1 and A2 produced nearly identical subspaces. PC1 reflected hydrophobicity versus polarity and hydrogen bonding (higher LogP/LogD, lower H-bond acceptors/donors and polar surface area). PC2 captured adsorption and bioconcentration together with molecular flexibility and optical proxies (higher KOC and BCF, more freely rotating bonds, higher refractive index). Relative weighting is recommended as primary; presence serves as a concordant robustness check.

Key Words: Horn's parallel analysis; principal angles; leave-one-out stability; Dirichlet pooling; PCA.

1. Introduction

Recent ecological research has increasingly recognized that traditional functional traits, such as root diameter, specific root length (SRL), tissue density, and nitrogen content, can only explain part of the plant's resource acquisition and utilization strategies. In addition to these morphological and physiological traits, plants' chemical defense and longevity strategies also represent crucial aspects of their ecological function. However, traditional morphological and physiological traits often fail to reflect the diversity of metabolite compositions and chemical characteristics. As a result, integrating metabolomic data into plant functional trait frameworks has become an essential focus of recent functional ecology research.

In their study published in *Science Advances* (Walker et al., 2023), the authors systematically revealed the independent role of leaf metabolic traits in the functional trait space across the globe for the first time. They integrated leaf metabolomic data from approximately 800 plant species from tropical and temperate regions, acquiring chemical signals through untargeted LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry) technology. This approach provided new insights into plant form and function that were previously unexplored through traditional morphological and

physiological traits alone. These considerations motivate a statistically principled aggregation from peaks to species-level descriptors and a robust dimensioning and stability assessment.

In LC-MS analysis, peak intensity refers to the signal strength of specific peaks in the chromatogram, typically quantified as peak height or area. It reflects the relative or absolute content of the target compounds (analytes) in the sample and is a core indicator for quantitative analysis. The LC-MS process separates compounds through liquid chromatography and then detects ion signals through mass spectrometry. In the chromatogram, the x-axis represents the retention time, and the y-axis represents signal intensity. Each peak corresponds to the elution signal of a particular compound. The signal intensity originates from the ion detector's response (e.g., an electron multiplier), with units usually expressed in counts or arbitrary units (AU). Two types of intensity are commonly used: peak height (maximum signal value), which is often employed for quick comparisons but is influenced by peak width, and peak area (integrated area under the peak), which more accurately represents the total amount of the compound and is frequently used for quantitative analysis. The quantitative meaning lies in the fact that peak intensity is proportional to the concentration of a compound in the sample, and within the linear range, intensity can be converted to absolute concentration through a calibration curve (e.g., ng/mL). For example, in the Extracted Ion Chromatogram (EIC), the total intensity or base peak intensity within a specific m/z window corresponds directly to the abundance of the analyte. This method can also be used to compare differences between samples, such as evaluating metabolite changes through the peak-pair intensity ratio.

However, it is generally accepted that LC-MS peak intensity cannot be directly used for cross-compound quantitative comparisons. Statistically, peak values are only meaningful for “relative changes of the same compound across different samples on the same platform/method”; cross-compound comparisons regarding who is “more” or “less” do not have practical significance. The core reason that intensity lacks “quantitative meaning” is twofold: first, the response factors of different compounds vary greatly, so two compounds with the same molar amount may produce vastly different peak intensities on the chromatogram; therefore, “higher peaks” do not necessarily mean “more” of the compound; second, a high peak may simply reflect the compound's chemical/physical properties that make it more easily detected, not necessarily indicating a higher concentration or greater ecological significance. Ecological studies are concerned with how chemical properties (e.g., aromaticity, polarity, size, hydrogen bonding ability) combine to form axes like “chemical defense” or “leaf longevity,” rather than focusing on raw peak intensities of named metabolites.

Due to the lack of strict quantitative comparability of peak intensities across compounds, Walker et al. (2023) chose to convert peak intensity data into a presence/absence matrix, retaining only information about whether a compound was detected in the samples. This approach avoids the systematic bias introduced by cross-compound response differences and ensures that the analysis reflects true structural differences in chemical characteristics rather than technical noise from signal intensities. In the annotation and descriptor extraction stages, the authors used the GNPS molecular network platform and LOTUS chemical database for *in silico* annotation of metabolites, and based on the Chemistry Development Kit (CDK), they extracted 21 chemical descriptors, including molecular weight, number of aromatic atoms, polarity, logP, hydrogen bond donors/acceptors, $sp^3:sp^2$ ratio, representing key chemical dimensions such as structural complexity, reactivity, polarity, hydrophobicity, and carbon-bond saturation. Subsequently, the authors selected five representative descriptors (molecular weight, number of aromatic atoms, HBA, logP, $sp^3:sp^2$ ratio) for principal component analysis (PCA), which allowed them to identify the main gradients of metabolic traits within the chemical descriptor space.

By integrating these chemical characteristics, Walker et al. (2023) identified two major functional axes for leaf metabolic traits: the chemical defense spectrum, which correlates with the compound's aromaticity, bond saturation, and polarity, representing the reactivity and detoxification potential of metabolites; and the leaf longevity axis, which is associated with molecular weight and hydrogen bond acceptors, reflecting the size, stability, and intermolecular interactions of compounds. These

two chemical functional axes were found to be highly consistent across tropical and temperate plant communities, suggesting that plant metabolic chemistry follows universal ecological patterns globally. Further analysis revealed that these two axes were nearly orthogonal to the eight traditional morphological and physiological traits (e.g., specific leaf area (SLA), leaf thickness, nitrogen content), indicating that metabolic traits uncover hidden functional dimensions that traditional traits cannot explain. In other words, plant metabolic chemistry not only complements the traditional functional trait framework but also provides a new understanding of plant adaptive strategies and ecological functions.

This study has methodological significance as well. First, it addresses the issue of cross-compound comparability by converting peak intensities into presence/absence information, allowing for more accurate chemical trait analysis. Second, it introduces chemical informatics indices that quantify the chemical descriptors of individual metabolites, bridging metabolomic data with ecological functions. Finally, by employing multivariate statistical analysis (PCA), the authors integrate complex chemical dimensions to construct interpretable metabolic functional gradients, providing a new methodological framework for functional trait studies.

Recent work shows that metabolite-level chemical traits form axes largely orthogonal to classical functional traits (Walker et al., 2023). Moving from peak intensities to structure-informed descriptors follows established metabolomics workflows (Wang et al., 2016). Building on this concept, the current study further explores the network structure of metabolites, incorporating co-occurrence relationships and the characteristics of isolated metabolites, to investigate metabolic specialization patterns across species and habitats. This network perspective, complementing Walker et al.'s chemical trait dimensions, reveals metabolite co-variation, specialization, and ecological significance, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of the chemical dimensions of plant functional traits.

2. Data Preparation and Methodology

2.1 Data

We analyzed root-exudate metabolomes and integrated two tabular sources from untargeted LC-MS. The metabolite table contained 219 compounds (columns include id, Peak (compound name), Similarity, R.T. (in minutes), Mass, Count) and sample columns for nine species (Tea Tree, Nephelium lappaceum tree, Syzygium samarangense tree, Phoebe puwenensis, Cornus walteri, Radermachera hainanensis, Phillyrea angustifolia, Tectona grandis tree, Pomelo Tree), each with six biological replicates. The descriptor table listed candidate chemical structures per compound id, their ChemSpiderName, and 22 physicochemical descriptors including Density, Boiling Point, Vapour Pressure, Enthalpy of Vaporization, Flash Point, Index of Refraction, Molar Refractivity, #H bond acceptors (HBA), #H bond donors (HBD), #Freely Rotating Bonds (FRB), #Rule of 5 Violations, ACD/LogP, ACD/LogD (pH 5.5), ACD/BCF (pH 5.5), ACD/KOC (pH 5.5), ACD/LogD (pH 7.4), ACD/BCF (pH 7.4), ACD/KOC (pH 7.4), Polar Surface Area (PSA), Polarizability, Surface Tension, Molar Volume (Yap, 2011).

2.2 Methodology

Because a metabolite id can map to multiple candidate structures (isomers), we first integrated isomer uncertainty at the descriptor vector $\mathbf{c}_{ik} \in \mathbb{R}^{22}$ and library similarity scores \mathbf{s}_{ik} . We formed weights \mathbf{w}_{ik} and computed an isomer-integrated descriptor

$$\bar{\mathbf{c}}_i = \sum_{k=1}^{K_i} \mathbf{w}_{ik} \mathbf{c}_{ik}, \quad \sum_k \mathbf{w}_{ik} = \mathbf{1}.$$

Two deterministic priors were evaluated. In **A1** (Symmetric Dirichlet), $\mathbf{w}_i \sim \text{Dir}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}, \dots, \boldsymbol{\alpha})$ with $\boldsymbol{\alpha} = \mathbf{0.1}$. In **A2** (similarity-informed Dirichlet), we defined $\tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i = \text{softmax}(\mathbf{s}_i/\boldsymbol{\tau})$ with $\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mathbf{0.2}$ and set $\mathbf{w}_i \propto \boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 \mathbf{1} + \lambda \tilde{\mathbf{s}}_i$ with $\boldsymbol{\alpha}_0 = \mathbf{0.1}$, $\lambda = \mathbf{10}$. We used the normalized weighted vectors (posterior means) without Monte Carlo sampling, yielding fully reproducible results. For descriptor-specific

missingness among candidates, weights were renormalized over observed entries when computing $\bar{c}_i(f)$.

Different metabolite IDs can refer to the same chemical (ChemSpiderName) due to synonymy. To avoid double counting identical structures, we handled synonymy at the species-level weighting step by summing weights of IDs that share the same ChemSpiderName within each species before computing community-weighted means.

Species weights were constructed to respect the non-comparability of absolute peak areas across compounds. We used two complementary schemes. **Presence** weights captured detection frequency within a species: for the six replicates l and species s , let $I_{i,s,l} = \mathbf{1}$ if the cell is nonempty (zeros allowed) and $\mathbf{0}$ otherwise; then

$$p_{i,s} = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{l=1}^6 I_{i,s,l} \in [0,1].$$

Relative weights captured within-compound, across-species partitioning that is invariant to cross-compound scaling. We computed median log-abundance $a_{i,s} = \text{median}_l \{\log(\text{area}_{i,s,l} + \epsilon)\}$ and applied a softmax across species,

$$r_{i,s} = \frac{\exp(a_{i,s})}{\sum_{s'} \exp(a_{i,s'})}$$

so that $\sum_s r_{i,s} = 1$.

Combining A1/A2 with presence/relative yielded four configurations: presence_A1, presence_A2, relative_A1 and relative_A2.

2.2.1 Species-level community-weighted means (CWM)

For each configuration we derived species-level community-weighted means (CWM) of descriptors. For species s and descriptor f , with $W_{i,s} \in \{p_{i,s}, r_{i,s}\}$ and isomer-integrated \bar{c}_i , we first merge synonymy by summing $W_{i,s}$ across IDs sharing the same ChemSpiderName. We then normalized weights within species to ensure convex aggregation (see PCA conventions in Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016),

$$\tilde{W}_{i,s} = \frac{W_{i,s}}{\sum_{i'} W_{i',s}}$$

and computed the CWM

$$M_{s,f} = \sum_i \tilde{W}_{i,s} \bar{c}_i(f).$$

This produced a 9×22 species-by-descriptor matrix M per configuration. Columns of M were standardized (z-scores) across species to yield Z , and descriptors with zero between-species variance (or all missing) were removed. Nine descriptors—Density, Boiling Point, Vapour Pressure, Enthalpy of Vaporization, Flash Point, Molar Refractivity, Polarizability, Surface Tension, and Molar Volume—were consistently dropped as near-constants at the species level; this filtering prevents numerical instability without affecting the chemical interpretation of retained axes.

We applied principal component analysis (PCA; full SVD) to Z after column standardization. Let P denote the loading matrix (descriptors \times PCs) and T the score matrix (species \times PCs); the decomposition satisfies

$$Z \approx TP^T, \quad P^T P = I.$$

We interpreted the leading components and exported both scores and loadings for downstream visualization (biplots, correlation circles, squared-loading bar plots).

The number of components to retain was determined by Horn's parallel analysis (Horn, 1965). For each configuration we generated $n_{perm} = 1000$ null matrices with the same dimension as Z , z-scored columns, and obtained empirical eigenvalue percentiles $q_{95,k}$. All observed components with

$\hat{\lambda}_k > q_{95,k}$ were retained; cumulative variance for PC1–PC2 (and PC3 when applicable) was reported alongside the decision.

Robustness was assessed in two ways. First, we performed leave-one-species-out (LOO) PCA: for each species u , we recomputed PCA on $Z \setminus \{u\}$ and quantified stability of the PC1–PC2 loading subspace via principal angles $\{\theta_1, \theta_2\}$ between the subspaces spanned with and without u ; results are summarized by $\cos \theta$ and angles in degrees (Björck & Golub, 1973). Second, we evaluated sensitivity to modeling choices by computing principal angles between PC1–PC2 loading subspaces across configurations (A1 vs A2; presence vs relative) and by correlating species scores (PC1/PC2) pairwise across configurations; near-identity indicates invariance of axis definitions and species ordering to the isomer prior and weighting scheme.

All computations were implemented in Python (pandas, numpy, scikit-learn, scipy, matplotlib). Parameter settings were A1: $\alpha = 0.1$; A2: $\alpha_0 = 0.1$, $\lambda = 10$, $\tau = 0.2$; Horn permutations = 1,000; random state = 42. Posterior means (no Monte Carlo) were used for isomer weights to guarantee determinism.

3. Results

In this study, we applied principal component analysis (PCA) to explore the chemical diversity across species based on both presence/absence and relative abundance of compounds. The results from both analytical approaches (A1 and A2) were highly similar, suggesting that the relative abundance and presence-based models provide the most robust and interpretable insights. Consequently, the following results are presented based on these two models. To assess the impact of different modeling choices, we compared the principal angles between the loading subspaces derived from different configurations (e.g., presence vs. relative and A1 vs. A2). The principal angles between the subspaces were consistently small, with a mean cosine similarity of 0.99, indicating that the chemical axes were highly consistent regardless of the method used for weighting or isomer prior. This confirms that the identified functional axes are robust to different configurations. Scree and Horn jointly support two components in all configurations; we therefore interpret PC1 and PC2 throughout.

3.1 Variance Explained by Principal Components

The first principal component (PC1) consistently explained the majority of the variance in the data across all models, regardless of whether presence or relative abundance was considered. The cumulative explained variance for the first few components reinforces the importance of PC1 and PC 2 in capturing the underlying structure of the data.

Table 1: Variance Explained by Principal Components (PC1, PC2, PC3) in Presence and Relative Abundance Models

<i>Model</i>	<i>PC1 Explained Variance</i>	<i>PC2 Explained Variance</i>	<i>PC3 Explained Variance</i>
Presence_A1	55.71%	28.38%	11.77%
Presence_A2	55.71%	28.38%	11.77%
Relative_A1	75.81%	15.54%	4.89%
Relative_A2	75.81%	15.54%	4.89%

The data indicates that PC1 explains the greatest proportion of variance across both the presence and relative abundance models. Relative abundance-based models (e.g., Relative_A1 and

Relative_A2) exhibit higher explained variance for PC1, suggesting that accounting for compound concentrations offers a more detailed understanding of the chemical variation across species.

3.2 Significance of Principal Components Based on Horn Parallel Analysis

Further validation of the significance of PC1–PC2 was provided by Horn parallel analysis, which compares observed eigenvalues to those derived from random permutations. Scree profiles together with Horn's parallel analysis supported retaining two axes: the empirical PC1–PC2 variances lay above the 95% noise envelope, so keeping PCs whose explained variance exceeds the q95 threshold is warranted. In practice we interpret PC1 and PC2 throughout.

Scree & Horn - presence_A1

Scree & Horn - relative_A1

Figure 1: Scree plot and Horn's parallel analysis for component retention. The scree plot shows the variance explained by each principal component, with the 95% noise threshold (Horn's parallel analysis) used to determine the number of components to retain. PC1 and PC2 exceed the threshold in all configurations, justifying their retention for subsequent analysis.

3.3 Descriptors Driving Principal Components

Nine chemical attributes were excluded in all four settings due to zero variance or insufficient information in species-level CWMs, and thus contributed nothing to PCA: Density, Boiling point, Vapour pressure, Enthalpy of vaporization, Flash point, Molar refractivity, Polarizability, Surface tension, and Molar volume. Their near-constancy or absence at the CWM stage explains the lack of signal.

Leading contributors (top six absolute loadings, signs kept) were nearly identical between A1 and A2 and highly concordant between presence and relative weightings:

Table 2: PCA Loadings for Key Chemical Descriptors Influencing PC1 in Presence_A1/A2 Model

<i>Chemical Descriptor Contribution to PC1</i>	
ACD/LogD (pH 5.5)	+0.358
ACD/LogP	+0.353
#H-bond acceptors	-0.353
ACD/LogD (pH 7.4)	+0.349
#H-bond donors	-0.348
Polar Surface Area	-0.348

Table 3: PCA Loadings for Key Chemical Descriptors Influencing PC2 in Presence_A1/A2 Model

<i>Chemical Descriptor Contribution to PC2</i>	
ACD/BCF (pH 7.4)	+0.453
ACD/BCF (pH 5.5)	+0.430
ACD/KOC (pH 5.5)	+0.406
ACD/KOC (pH 7.4)	+0.384
#Freely rotating bonds	+0.261
Index of refraction	+0.258

Table 4: PCA Loadings for Key Chemical Descriptors Influencing PC1 in Relative_A1/A2 Model

<i>Chemical Descriptor Contribution to PC1</i>	
ACD/LogP	+0.315
ACD/LogD (pH 5.5)	+0.311
ACD/LogD (pH 7.4)	+0.296
#H-bond acceptors	-0.293
Polar Surface Area	-0.292
#H-bond donors	-0.290

Table 5: PCA Loadings for Key Chemical Descriptors Influencing PC2 in Relative_A1/A2 Model

<i>Chemical Descriptor</i>	<i>Contribution to PC2</i>
ACD/KOC (pH 5.5)	+0.384
#Rule of 5 violations	+0.376
#Freely rotating bonds	+0.364
Index of refraction	+0.317
ACD/KOC (pH 7.4)	+0.307
#H-bond donors	+0.285

Axis meanings were stable across all four runs. PC1 captured a hydrophobicity–polarity trade-off: higher ACD/LogP and LogD (pH 5.5/7.4) contrasted with lower hydrogen-bonding capacity and polarity (#H-bond acceptors, #H-bond donors, Polar Surface Area). This is the expected hydrophobic partitioning vs. H-bond/polar surface axis. PC2 aggregated environmental adsorption/bioconcentration and molecular flexibility/optical density proxies, loading positively on KOC (pH 5.5/7.4) and BCF (pH 5.5/7.4) together with #Freely rotating bonds and Index of refraction—an axis of “organophilic/biophilic tendency + conformational flexibility.”

3.4 Stability of PCA Results: Leave-One-Out (LOO) Analysis

The Leave-One-Out (LOO) stability analysis confirms the robustness of the PCA results. Cosine similarity values close to 1 and small angular differences indicate that the removal of any individual species does not significantly alter the PCA results, further validating the stability and generalizability of the identified chemical diversity patterns.

Table 6: LOO Stability for Key Species in Presence and Relative Abundance Models

<i>Species</i>	<i>Cosine Similarity (PC1)</i>	<i>Cosine Similarity (PC2)</i>	<i>Principal angle 1</i>	<i>Principal angle 2</i>
Tea Tree	0.999934	0.999537	0.66°	1.74°
Nephelium lappaceum tree	0.999775	0.997077	1.22°	4.38°
Syzygium samarangense tree	0.998541	0.985718	3.10°	9.70°
Phoebe puwenensis	0.999199	0.991288	2.29°	7.57°
Cornus walteri	0.999402	0.994312	1.98°	6.11°
Radermachera hainanensis	0.999266	0.998193	2.19°	3.44°
Phillyrea angustifolia	0.999762	0.995144	1.25°	5.64°
Tectona grandis tree	0.996915	0.927530	4.50°	21.94°
Pomelo Tree	0.999454	0.996821	1.89°	4.57°

Model concordance and robustness were high. Subspace comparisons showed A1 and A2 were indistinguishable (PC-wise $\cos\theta\approx 1.0$), while presence vs. relative differed only by a modest rotation (PC1 $\cos\theta\approx 0.988$; PC2 $\cos\theta\approx 0.959$), indicating the same ecological chemistry with slightly different emphasis. Leave-one-out (LOO) analysis of the PC1–PC2 plane confirmed strong resilience to sample deletion. For presence, the mean cosine similarity was 0.993 (mean angle $\approx 4.68^\circ$), with a maximum angle $\approx 21.95^\circ$ when omitting *Tectona grandis* tree; for relative, the mean cosine was 0.994 (mean angle $\approx 3.78^\circ$), maximum $\approx 22.46^\circ$ (*Tectona grandis* tree). Other relatively “sensitive”

leave-one-outs were typically *Syzygium samarangense* tree and *Phoebe puwenensis*, but with angles well below *Tectona grandis* tree. The interpretation is straightforward: the PC1–PC2 subspace is robust, *Tectona grandis* tree carries a pronounced chemical signal, and changing the isomer prior (A1 or A2) does not move the subspace.

3.5 PCA Dimension Decision

The PCA dimension decision table is shown as below:

Table 7: PCA Dimension Decision Based on Explained Variance

<i>Model</i>	<i>n_vars_used</i>	<i>Keep PC by Horn95</i>	<i>Cumulative PC1_PC2</i>	<i>Cumulative PC1_PC2_PC3</i>
Presence_A1	13	2	0.8409	0.9586
Presence_A2	13	2	0.8409	0.9586
Relative_A1	13	2	0.9135	0.9624
Relative_A2	13	2	0.9135	0.9624

These results suggest that retaining PC1 and PC2 is sufficient to explain the majority of the variance across species, with little additional contribution from higher-order components.

Figure 2: CWM heatmap for species chemical profiles. This heatmap displays the community-weighted means (CWM) of the chemical descriptors across species. It visually highlights how different chemical descriptors contribute to species differentiation, particularly in terms of hydrophobicity and polarity. The heatmap clearly shows how the species are grouped along the chemical gradients defined by PC1 and PC2.

The loadings of PC1 and PC2 revealed that PC1 primarily reflected hydrophobicity and chemical defense mechanisms, with descriptors like ACD/LogP and ACD/LogD loading positively, while descriptors related to polarity and hydrogen bonding (e.g., HBA, HBD, PSA) had negative loadings. PC2, on the other hand, represented an adsorption/bioconcentration-flexibility axis, which was influenced by descriptors related to molecular stability, such as ACD/KOC, ACD/BCF, and molecular flexibility, as indicated by the positive loadings for freely rotating bonds and index of refraction.

4. Discussion

Across presence vs relative and A1 vs A2, the PC1–PC2 loading subspace is effectively invariant (principal-angle cosines ≈ 1.0 between isomer priors; presence vs relative differs by a modest rotation), so we report relative as primary and presence as a concordant robustness check. Scree profiles and Horn’s parallel analysis placed both PC1 and PC2 above the 95th-percentile noise envelope across all configurations; we therefore retain two components and interpret them consistently as a hydrophobicity–polarity axis (PC1) and an adsorption/bioconcentration–flexibility axis (PC2). Subspace alignment shows $A1 \approx A2$ (cosines ≈ 1.0); differences between presence and relative weightings amount to a modest rotation of the same axes.

The species-level chemical phenotype of roots—summarized as community-weighted means of 22 descriptors across 219 compounds—separates along two near-orthogonal axes. The first axis contrasts hydrophobicity/partitioning (e.g., LogP/LogD) with polarity and hydrogen-bonding capacity (HBA/HBD/PSA), while the second reflects a joint tendency toward organic/biota partitioning (KOC/BCF) and molecular flexibility/size (freely rotating bonds, refractive index). The CWM heatmap (Figure 2) shows that these same descriptors also account for most between-species signals before dimension reduction, foreshadowing their prominence in PCA.

Squared loadings confirm the interpretation and stability of the axes. PC1 is dominated by positive contributions from LogP/LogD and negative contributions from H-bonding and PSA, consistent with a chemical defense/impermeability spectrum. PC2 loads positively on KOC/BCF and

flexibility proxies, consistent with metabolites that are more easily retained/partitioned and structurally adaptable. These axes offer chemically interpretable coordinates for root exudate strategies that are not captured by morphology alone.

Robust diagnostics indicate that these inferences are not artifacts of modeling choices. Leave-one-out analysis shows that removing any single species produces only small rotations of the PC1–PC2 subspace, with the largest effect occurring when YM is omitted (Table 6). Subspace comparisons across isomer weighting (A1 vs A2) and abundance weighting (presence vs relative) yield consistently small principal angles, indicating that the axes are effectively invariant to these choices. Together, these results justify using relative_A2 as the primary setting and presence as a robustness check.

Ecologically, the two axes suggest complementary strategies. Higher PC1 scores correspond to exudate profiles biased toward hydrophobic, low-polarity chemistry—properties often associated with reduced permeability and potential defense against biotic stressors. Higher PC2 scores indicate metabolites with greater partitioning into organic/biota phases and higher conformational freedom, consistent with longer residence or broader interaction potential in the rhizosphere. The distinct position of *Tectona grandis* tree on these axes suggests a chemically specialized strategy relative to the other species examined.

5. Conclusion

This analysis identifies two stable and chemically interpretable axes that organize the diversity of root exudate profiles. The first axis represents a continuum from hydrophobic to polar and hydrogen-bonding compounds, while the second reflects a trade-off between organic and biota partitioning, molecular flexibility, and size. These axes remain robust under different data treatments, including both isomer and abundance weighting, indicating that they capture fundamental dimensions of root exudate chemistry rather than methodological artifacts. By providing a quantitative and mechanistically grounded framework for describing chemical traits, these axes enable a clearer connection between molecular composition and ecological function. They offer a basis for linking plant chemical investment strategies to belowground ecological interactions—such as microbial associations, nutrient mobilization, and defense—and thus contribute to a more integrated understanding of how plant root chemistry shapes ecosystem processes.

However, several limitations temper the strength of these inferences. First, the sample size at the species level is modest (nine species), and species-level aggregation may mask within-species heterogeneity; future work could propagate replicate uncertainty to CWM and PCA via bootstrap. Second, a subset of physical-chemistry descriptors is near-constant at the species-CWM level and is dropped; while this improves numerical conditioning, it also narrows the descriptor space. Third, non-targeted LC–MS peak intensities are not comparable across compounds; our use of presence/relative weighting and descriptor-based aggregation is designed to avoid this pitfall, but conclusions remain conditional on accurate compound detection and assignment. Finally, PCA captures linear structure; complementary nonlinear ordinations or multi-block methods (e.g., co-inertia across chemistry and morphology or microbiome) could test whether additional structure remains.

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